

Review of Archaeological Investigations in the Protohistoric and Historical Archaeology of Vidarbha

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Abstract

During the colonial and post-colonial periods, the study of protohistoric and historical archaeology in Vidarbha witnessed various phases of research. This paper endeavors to understand research concepts and contributions at individual and institutional levels, since the beginning of antiquarian studies in this region.

Introduction

The region of Vidarbha forms the eastern part of Maharashtra, India. Protohistoric Chalcolithic human settlements in this region began around the first millennium BCE, as noted at sites such as Adam (IAR 1990-91, 1991-92), Arambha (IAR 1991-92), Shirkanda (IAR 1991-92), and Tuljapur Garhi (Bopardikar 1996). However at most sites, human occupation started from the Iron Age (c. 800-700 BCE) characterized by megalithic burials; which barring a few exceptions are not observed in other parts of Maharashtra. Research into the protohistoric and historical archaeology of India in general and of Vidarbha in particular, witnessed various phases of development during the colonial and post-colonial periods; owing to changing conceptual and analytical approaches. This paper attempts to review these seminal contributions at individual as well as institutional level, results of important excavations and changes in research outlooks along with investigation methods in the field of protohistoric and historical archaeology, in Vidarbha since the 19th century.

Excavations

Excavations in various parts of Vidarbha carried out by the Archaeological Survey India (hereafter ASI), Maharashtra State Department of Archaeology and Museums (hereafter MSDAM), Nagpur University, Deccan College, and efforts made at individual levels (especially during the colonial period) are worth mentioning (see Table 1).

In recent years, a few more sites have been excavated, viz., Vyahad (Megalithic site) by Nagpur University, Bhandak (Early Historic site) by MSDAM and Nagpur University, and Chandankheda (Early Historic site) by Nagpur University and MSDAM; but their reports are yet to be published.

Phases of Development

In the following paragraphs we briefly discuss various phases of development, from the earliest to recent times, of protohistoric and historical archaeology in Vidarbha.

Phase I. The Beginning: Individual Efforts (1850-1870)

Rev. Hislop

Rev. Hislop (1817-1863) (Scottish Missionary) was a well known evangelist, educationist¹ and a geologist. His important contribution is in geological research in the Nagpur area (Hislop 1857, 1861a, 1861b). Apart from his extensive geological research, he also excavated a stone circle near Nagpur. The details of the excavation were published in the form of a letter in 1857 in *Journal of Bombay Branch of Royal Asiatic Society*. In the letter, he refers to his excavations at Takalghat and general abundance of these burial remains in the Nagpur district. The paragraph in his letter reads:

[...] Several years ago I dug it out of a Scythian stone-circle, at Takalghat, 20 miles S. of Nagpur. When it was brought to light, at the height of about half an inch from the bottom it was covered over with fragments of pottery fitted to each other so as to form

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1. There is a college named after him in Nagpur.

Table 1: Details of the Excavated Sites in Vidarbha

Site*	District	Excavating Agency/ person	Reference
Takalaghat	Nagpur	Rev. Hislop	Hislop 1857: 671-72
Wurreegaon (Kamptee)	Nagpur	G.G. Pearse	Pearse 1869: 207-217
Khairwada (also spelt as Khaiwarra) (21° 1' N; 78° 29' E)	Wardha	First by J.J. Carey; Later by Deccan College and MSDAM	Carey 1871: 238-39; IAR 1981-82: 51-52
Junapani	Nagpur	First by Rivett-Carnac; Later by ASI	Rivett-Carnac 1879; IAR 1961-62: 32-33
Kaundinyapur (20° 55' N; 78° 05' E)	Amravati	First by MSDAM; Later by Deccan College	Dikshit 1968; Mishra <i>et al.</i> In press. (also see Smith 2001)
Paunar (20° 47' N; 78° 41' E)	Wardha	Nagpur University	Deo and Dhavalikar 1968
Takalghat-Khapa (20° 54' 40" N; 78° 56' 30" E)	Nagpur	Nagpur University	Deo 1970a
Pauni (20° 48' N; 79° 39' E)	Bhandara	First by Nagpur University and ASI; Later by ASI	Deo and Joshi 1972; Nath 1998
Mahurjhari (21° 14' N; 79° 30' E)	Nagpur	First by Nagpur University; Later by Deccan College	Deo 1973a; IAR 2001-02: 123-128; IAR 2002-03: 172-174; Mohanty 2002, 2003a, 2003b
Mandhal	Nagpur	Nagpur University	Shastri 1978
Arni (20° 4' N; 78° 57' E)	Yavatmal	Nagpur University	IAR 1978-79: 71-72, IAR 1984-85: 55-56
Nagra	Gondia (earlier in Bhandara)	MSDAM	IAR 1979-80: 56; IAR 1980-81: 40
Boregaon (21° 20' N; 78° 55' E)	Nagpur	Deccan College and MSDAM	IAR 1980-81: 40
Naikund (21° 20' N; 79° 10' E)	Nagpur	MSDAM and Deccan College	Deo and Jamkhedkar 1982
Bhagi Mahari (21° 24' N; 78° 51' E)	Nagpur	MSDAM and Deccan College	IAR 1982-83: 61-62, IAR 1983-84: 57-58
Mulachera (19° 41' N; 80° 01' E)	Gadchiroli	MSDAM	IAR 1988-89: 49, IAR 1987-88: 84
Adam (21° 00' N; 79° 28' E)	Nagpur	ASI	IAR 1988-89: 50-62; IAR 1990-91: 45-50; IAR 1991-92: 63-68; Nath 1992a: 69-79
Tharsa (21° 15' N; 21° 15' E)	Nagpur	Nagpur University	IAR 1989-90: 58-60
Arambha (20° 34' N; 78° 59' E)	Nagpur	ASI	IAR 1991-92: 73-74
Shirkhanda	Nagpur	ASI	IAR 1991-92: 68-69
Raipur (21° 43' N; 78° 58' E)	Nagpur	Deccan College	Deglurkar and Lad 1992
Pachkheri (20° 55' N; 79° 30' E)	Nagpur	ASI	IAR 1992-93: 64-73
Bhawar (20° 52' N; 79° 44' E)	Bhandara	ASI	IAR 1992-93: 55-62
Mansar (21° 24' N; 79° 17' E)	Nagpur	ASI	IAR 1994-95: 55-57; IAR 1997-98: 129-133; IAR 1998-99: 114-116; IAR 1999-2000: 103-106; Joshi and Sharma 2000: 127-131; 2005: 1-26
Tuljapur Garhi (21° 12' N; 77° 38' E)	Amaravti	ASI	Bopardikar 1996
Hamlapuri	Nagpur	MSDAM	Sali 1998
Washim	Washim	MSDAM	Sali 1998
Vivekanandpur	Gadchiroli	MSDAM	Sali 1998

Site*	District	Excavating Agency/ person	Reference
Bramhapuri (20°37' N; 79°50' E) Dhamma (Ling) (21° 8'30' N; 78° 51' E)	Chandrapur Nagpur	Deccan College Nagpur University	Walimbe 2003: 39-40 IAR 2001-02: 121-123, IAR 2002-03: 168-172; Gupta and Ismail 2005: 51-65
Paturda (76° 44' E; 20° 57' N) Bhon (20° 55' N; 76° 39' E)	Buldana Buldana	Deccan College Deccan College	Deotare 2007 Deotare 2007; Deotare <i>et al.</i> 2007: 177-185; Deotare <i>et al.</i> 2008: 210-216
Kholapur (20° 57' N; 77° 31' E)	Amaravati	Deccan College	Deotare 2009: 63-66

* latitude & longitude are given wherever available; sites are arranged as per their year of publication

Fig. 1: Sketch of barrows (stone circles) near Nagpur (Reproduced from Rivett-Carnac 1879)

a kind of mosaic work, evidently to protect the ashes which were deposited in it. In the same cairn were found a spear-head, a piece of iron like a large knife or hatchet, nail, &c. At Takalghat there is a wide field for the antiquary. Indeed the country all round abounds in Scythian remains, but it would require a person with much leisure for their investigation. I am acquainted with about twenty localities where there are circles, and eight villages where there are kistavens in this district. (Hislop 1857: 671-72)

The exact year of excavation was not mentioned by Hislop in this letter, but perhaps this is the

earliest known attempt in investigating the history of Vidarbha. What is important is the mention of Scythian stone-circles which indicates an understanding of this topic. Unfortunately Rev. Hislop drowned in the Bori river, in the vicinity of Takalaghat in 1863 at the age of 45.

J.H. Rivett-Carnac

John Henry Rivett-Carnac (1838-1923) was in the Bengal Civil Service. The first well documented exploration and excavation in the Vidarbha region dates back to 1867 and was undertaken by J.H.

Fig. 2: Rough survey of stone circles near Junapani (Reproduced from Rivett-Carnac 1879)

Rivett-Carnac, Alfred Lyall, and Blanford at the site of Junapani (Nagpur district) (Fig. 1). A rough map based on this survey was prepared by Rivett-Carnac indicating locations of various barrows near Junapani (Fig. 2). The ‘barrow’ (a term used for ‘stone-circle’) at Junapani was excavated by them in January 1867. They recovered iron implements such as arrowheads, spearheads, axes, snaffle bits, iron razors, knives/daggers, etc. (Rivett-Carnac 1879). Others were also looking into the problem of stone circles (barrows). As per Rivett-Carnac (1879: 1-16), stone circles in the vicinity of Nagpur were explored by Colonel Glasfurd, Major G.G. Pearse, and J. J. Carey. Hanna and Henry Dangerfield worked on stone circles at Junapani.

George Godfrey Pearse

The year 1867 proved important, as after Rivett-Carnac’s excavation in January, Major George Godfrey Pearse (1827-1905) of the Royal Artillery excavated at the site of Wurreegaon (one mile

from Kamptee, Nagpur district) in July. Details of the excavation were published in *The Journal of the Ethnological Society of London* in 1869 (Pearse 1869: 207-217). This paper, is perhaps the best example of detailed description and excellent observation although no advanced technique was developed for the excavation of stone circles. During the excavation, he came across vessels of black and brown and black ware. Black vessels had covers with cone-like tops. He also found some husks of coconut shells. An interesting description of human remains is also given:

‘On the 11th July 1867 (i.e. on the fifth day of excavating), at about 6 ½ feet depth, I found the remains of a man. [...] Part of skull, some teeth (one a molar one), are amongst the remains preserved. The body was 6 feet or 6 feet 1 inch long. The bones are of a large-skulled and large-boned person. [...] On the 12th July 1867 (that is on the sixth day of excavating) was found, on the same level as the first body, a second body of about the same size, parallel

Fig. 4: Iron implements from the site of Wurreegaon (Kamptee, Nagpur district) (Reproduced from Pearse 1869)

J.J. Carey

J.J. Carey, Executive Engineer, Khangaon, excavated a few stone circles at Khaiwarra (modern Khairwada, also spelt as - Khywarree by Rivett-Carnac) 24 km west of Arvi in District Wardha, probably in 1869. Each stone circle was termed a mound by Carey, and around 150 such so called mounds were noticed by him. Some of his observations are very interesting to note:

"The stone circles lately found by me near the village of Khaiwarra, about 10 miles east of Arvi in the Wardah district, were opened by desire of Mr. Morris, chief Commissioner, Central Provinces. [...] The mounds in every case were hollow at the top, making me think that a chamber would be found underneath, that the stones forming the ceiling had probably given away; but, on opening two, nothing was found to guarantee such an idea. [...]"

I commenced digging operation on the principal mound in the place, 40 x 43 in diameter, [...] Nothing

but loose stones and earth was removed, until about 15 inches from the surface broken red pottery began to show on the south side. At last some stiff leaden coloured clay was found, fast binding pieces of pottery, and on close examination large quantities of teeth were found, which evidently had been put into a *gurrah* and imbedded in this clay. These bones are, I believe, the back teeth of horses, in very good preservation. [...]"

[...] I saw a "find," and immediately jumped into the hole, and with the greatest care dug out of the clay, well cemented together, two copper bells, two round copper (in my opinion) ear-rings, and an iron-axe [...] this and a few iron implements and a gold ring were the only things found. The excavation was carried down about 2.6 feet.

In the other we went down over three feet from the surface [...] The only implement in good preservation was a kind of saucer for holding oil, which had a handle with a hook to hang by, and a

Fig. 5: Implements recovered from Junapani and Kamptee excavations (Reproduced from Leshnik 1970)

spiral spring, which must I think have been wound round a stick' (Carey 1871: 238-239).

Phase II. Period of Intensive Explorations (1870-1950)

Alexander Cunningham

Alexander Cunningham carried out an archaeological tour in 1873-74 and 74-75 covering the Central Provinces (Cunningham 1966, reprint). In the course of surveys he explored Chanda (modern Chandrapur district) and surrounding areas and reported various historical sites, such as Bhandak and its temple and cave complexes, caves at Dewalwâra, temples and other structural remains at Chanda, temples at Markandi, etc., (Cunningham 1966: 121-160).

Interestingly Cunningham also recorded two cromlechs or dolmens at the site of Keljhar, near Chanda. Cunningham did not otherwise show any interest in megalithic structures during his campaigns, hence this reference is important (Cunningham 1966: 140-141).

Henry Cousens

During the years 1892-93-94, Henry Cousens collected data regarding monuments, ancient sites, temples of Central provinces and Berar (Cousens 1971, reprint). In this book, he mentioned various stone circle and menhir sites in Vidarbha as well, such as Borgaon, Digras, Ghorar and Kohali, Junapani, Nildoh, Takalghat, Wathora, Charmursi, Keljhar, Wagnak, Sironcha, Pipalgaon, Telota Khairi (1971: 3-24). His comments on stone circles are interesting:

'These circles are of great age. No one can now say exactly what they are but it is commonly believed that they mark the site of temporary encampments of the Gavalis, or pastoral tribes who wandered from place to place with their cattle. Others say that such places were formerly used for interring dead bodies. Sometime iron nails and tools are found beneath the stones. Possibly they are of Scythian origin' (Cousens 1971: 5).

J.D.M. Beglar

Joseph Daviditch Melik Beglar had training in Civil Engineering and was working with the Public Works Department as an Assistant Engineer. He worked as Cunningham's assistant in the Archaeological Department from 1871 to 1879 (Singh 2004: 135-136). During his association with this department he carried out surveys in various parts of India (Beglar and Carlley 1874, Beglar 1878a, 1878b). During exploration in the Central Province in 1873-74, Beglar showed an awareness of the need to learn about the 'Old Road'. He observed:

'The Old Road appears to have come from some point near Bhandak or Dewalwâra, supposed to be the ancient Kundilpur (I cannot speak with confidence on this point, not having examined the country west of Nâgpur), through Deotek close past Palâsgarh, past Banjâri (a great mart for articles of traffic by pack animals), past Ámbâgarh Chowki (which possesses a small fort of no interest, and probably not very old), past Bâlod, Sorar, to Gowror, whence it branched

into two, one going *via* Kákér and Sehwá towards Ganjám, through the great fort of Jaugada, which contains one of Asoka's edicts; the other branch going past Dhamtari and Rájam, thence probably skirting the Mahanadi northwards past Savaripura, Savarinaran, & c., to Katak. The determination of these ancient lines of communications is of great importance; for my experience, little as it is, has shewn me that away from great lines of communications of ancient times few archaeological remains are to be met with; they are not spread about at random here and there in isolated spots, but *always* on the great old roads, and however isolated any particular remnant of antiquity may be at first sight, it will be found on close examination to be on some old line of road [...]. (Beglar 1878a: 140)

Apart from describing the old road from Vidarbha to Orissa, Beglar also tried to identify the ancient Kundilpur (or Kundina) with Bhandak or Dewalwara with some uncertainty. Beglar's attempt must be recognized for at least attempting an identification of a historical site of Vidarbha. Later, the site was identified with modern Kaundinyapur in Amaravati district. An interesting incident is also reported by Beglar on problems he faced at Ramtek, Nagpur, when he was forbidden by a group of Brahmins, to enter temples and inspect them in person (Beglar 1878a: 111-112).

Other Efforts

Apart from stone circle investigations, the first extensive survey at the historic site of Mansar (45 km north-east of Nagpur) was carried out by T.A. Wellsted as early as 1933, which brought to light antiquarian, epigraphical and structural remains of the Vakataka period around Hidimba tekdi. To the east of this hillock, structural remains of the great monastery were noticed (information cited in IAR 1994-95: 55-57).

The historic antiquity of Mahurjhari (Mahurziri – as spelt by Hunter) was brought to light by G. Hunter, and first published in the *Annual of the Sharadasrama* of Yeotmal in 1933. G. Hunter had come across bricks having size of 16''-17'' x 10''-11'' x 3'' - 3 ½''. He reported a seal with a box-headed script of the Gupta-Vakataka period. He also published data on a carnelian seal with the letters reading 'apumada' or 'apramada', an intaglio in Vakataka characters, an exact replica of the Proto-Elamite seal in red

sandstone, a seal in rock-crystal and a 'Naga' seal. He also reported finds of a Lajja-gauri plaque and beads, made of a variety of semi-precious stones (Hunter 1933: 30-35).

All these attempts were amateur, basically unorganized and individually inspired without any institutional backing, except for J.D. Beglar (A. Cunningham's assistant) who carried out government sponsored surveys in the central provinces but failed to identify the potential of any site for further investigation.

Phase III. In Search of Historical Identities: Post-Independence (1950-1970)

During the post-independence period, the ASI became active in this region. In concurrence with earlier attempts, many Indian scholars continued to explore and excavate megalithic sites. These included N.R. Banerjee who explored the site of Mahajari (Mahurjhari) near Junapani (IAR 1958-59: 21) and B.K. Thapar who excavated the site of Junapani (IAR 1961-62: 32-34) and others.

After independence, the state department and universities (Nagpur University, Deccan College) emerged, outside the ASI's scope. Foremost among these was the department of AIHC and Archaeology of Nagpur University (established in 1955). Located in the heartland of Vidarbha, it became an obvious hub of archaeological activities in this and surrounding regions. The MSDAM also rose on a strong footing. The result of this development was the first full-fledged excavation in Vidarbha which was carried out by the MSDAM and Nagpur University.

The first excavation at a historical site after independence took place at Kaundinyapur in Vidarbha in the years 1962 and 1964 (Dikshit 1968), although the historical importance and potential of the site, was clear as early as 1933 (Deshpande 1933: 36-46). The site was chosen for excavation since it was mentioned in the *Mahabharata*, in connection with the Krishna and Rukmini story (Rukmini was the daughter of the Vidarbha king, Bhisimak). The place called Kundina (modern Kaundinyapur) is also mentioned in the story of Nala and Damayanti, who was the daughter of the Vidarbha king Bhima. Thus, the first excavation after independence in Vidarbha was perhaps carried out with the aim of revealing the authenticity of these epic stories.

The next excavation, at Paunar in 1967 (Deo and Dhavalikar 1968) was carried out by Nagpur University. The site was selected probably due to the assumption put forward first by K.N. Dikshit, and supported by V.V. Mirashi, that modern Paunar was the site of the ancient Pravaraपुर, capital of the Vakatakas. However, according to the excavators, 'there is no confirmatory evidence to show that Paunar was the ancient capital Pravaraपुर. The excavations were confined to a very small area and that to on the periphery of the ancient mound near the river' (Deo and Dhavalikar 1968: 202). Recently the site of Mansar has been identified as the ancient Pravaraपुर by J.P. Joshi and A.K. Sharma, as mentioned in Vakataka inscriptions (see Joshi and Sharma 2005).

The next important excavation at Pauni was carried out in the year 1969-70 (Deo and Joshi 1972) again by Nagpur University in collaboration with the ASI. Despite early notices on the antiquity of the site as early as 1897 by Henry Cousens (1971: 24), the site was selected for excavation only when a local newspaper reported that a few sculptures and a massive coping stone fragment bearing an inscription in Brahmi characters, were found near a locality termed Jagannath Tekdi (Deo and Joshi 1972: 1). This excavation was very productive as it exposed the first stupa structure of Vidarbha. Important features along with the stupa structure were noted such as railing, *pradakshina patha*, gateways, pillars, and *chhatravali*.

What is important in this period is an increased awareness at the regional level which in turn resulted in an increase in the number of excavations and explorations, which extensively aided in understanding regional chronological profiles.

Phase IV. Excavations of Iron Age Sites and the Contribution of S.B. Deo (1970's -1980's)

This phase saw a shift in focus towards excavations and explorations of Iron Age - Megalithic sites. The unique feature of the Vidarbha region lies in the large uniqueness of Megalithic circles and the iron and copper implements associated with these circles. Excavations at various megalithic sites, (burial and habitation), unearthed Vidarbha's very own culture different from that of South India in many respects. This culture is totally absent in the rest of Maharashtra. From the 1970's onwards various

important Iron Age-Megalithic sites were excavated, such as Takalghat-Khapa, Mahurjhari, Arni, Khairwada, Boregaon, Naikund, Bhagimahari, Adam, Tharsa, Arambha, Shirkhanda, Bhawar, Pachkheri, etc. (see Table 1).

The Contribution of S.B. Deo

S.B. Deo (1923-1996) contributed immensely towards understanding the Vidarbha Megalithic culture. His interest in the Iron Age-Megalithic culture of this region led to a number of excavations in this area. He studied almost all aspects of the Megalithic culture like pottery, tool techniques, house plans, subsistence, authors of the culture, etc. He is credited for being the first to obtain ¹⁴C date for the Vidarbha Megalithic habitation site, Takalghat and for providing a specific time bracket which was lacking earlier (Deo 1969, 1970a, 1970b, 1973a, 1973b 1973c, 1973d, 1982).

In 1966 he was appointed as Professor and Head of the Department of Ancient Indian History Culture and Archaeology at Nagpur University and remained there for eight years. During this period he efficiently carried out excavations at Paunar (1967), Takalghat-Khapa (1967-68), Pauni (1968-70), Mahurjhari (1971-72) and Bhokardan (1973-74). He joined Deccan College in 1974 as a professor of Proto-Indian and Ancient Indian History, and became the Director in 1978, retiring in the same capacity in 1985. Important excavations carried out during his tenure were at Ter (1974), Apegaon (1976-77), Naikund (1977-78, 79-80), Mahurjhari (1978-79), Boregaon (1980-81), Khairwada (1981-82), Bhagimohari (1983-84) and Raipur (1985). Reports of six sites were published.

Phase V. Iron Age Studies: Scientific Approaches and the Contribution of Deccan College (1980-2000)

Crucial changes in research strategies regarding Iron Age-Megalithic studies are noted during 1980-2000. This phase witnessed the use of intensive scientific methods to understand various aspects of this culture. This phase also coincided with the establishment of various laboratories at the Deccan College, a unique feature in India.

With respect to the archaeology of the Vidarbha region, these laboratories significantly contributed in the following fields: palaeoanthropological work

(Walimbe 1988, 1992), palaeobotanical work (Kajale 1989, 1994), ancient iron technology (Gogte 1980; Gogte *et al.* 1982; Gogte *et al.* 1984), chemical analysis of soil (Deotare 1984, Kshirsagar 1992), chemical analysis of pottery (Gogte and Kshirsagar 1992, 1996), XRD analysis for pottery (Gogte 1992), archaeozoology (Thomas 1992a, 1992b, 1993, 1995, 1996, Thomas *et al. in press*), and demography (Mohanty and Walimbe 1993, 1996).

This phase also saw extensive excavations at Early Historic site of Adam (Nagpur) by the ASI (IAR 1988-89, 89-90, 90-91, 91-92).

Phase VI. Multi-disciplinary Approaches: The Current Theme (2000 onwards)

The beginning of the new millennium saw new approaches in early historical archaeology resulting in important excavations by the Deccan College (Bramhapuri 2002, Paturda 2002, Mahurjhari 2003-05, Bhon 2003-2007, Kholapur 2008-09); Nagpur University (Dhamna Linga 2003-04, Vyahad 2006); and Nagpur University with the MSDAM (Bhandak 2007, Chandankheda 2010).

Conservation and Reconstruction

As a result of a collaborative project between Deccan College, Pune and the Indira Gandhi Rashtriya Manav Sangrahalay (Museum of Mankind), Bhopal, the Iron Age-Megalithic site of Mahurjhari in Vidarbha was excavated by a team led by R. Mohanty of the Deccan College and one of the megaliths was transported and displayed as an open-air exhibit in IGRMS campus at Bhopal (Fig. 6) (Mohanty 2006: 77-80).

Studies of Climate Change

A few attempts were made to understand climate change occurring during the early historic period. Deotare (2006: 517-526) attempted to study late Holocene climate change on the basis of archaeological evidence from the Purna basin. He used archaeological evidence from the excavated sites – Bhon (Pre-Satavahana and Satavahana 3rd-4th century BCE to 2nd century CE) and Paturda (Post-Gupta 5th to 9th century CE). The study of botanical remains from these sites yielded a high proportion of rice grains as well as rice husk (about 50%), wheat, *jowar*, green gram, grass pea, black gram, pigeon pea and common pea from Bhon. Cereals like *jowar* (about 30%), pulses like black gram, green gram,

pea, etc. were recovered from Paturda. The presence of rice (50% of the total grains recovered) which requires water in abundance indicated a favorable climate. On the other hand, evidence from Paturda with marginal recovery of grains such as millets, pulses, indicated deterioration in agricultural practices due to an unfavorable climate (Deotare 2006: 517-526).

S. Sathe's doctoral research (2008) at Deccan College focused on a qualitative and quantitative analysis of palynomorphs and other evidence from sedimentology, mineral magnetics, chronology, and phytogeography, at the site of Mansar (district Nagpur, Historical site) from lake deposits. This approach was adopted to reconstruct past vegetation and environmental history, in the late Holocene period, particularly over the last 2000 years.

Study of State Formation Processes in Vidarbha

The author attempted to study the archaeo-historical profile of the Vidarbha region from the c. 6th century BCE to 5 - 6th century CE; in order to reconstruct the process of state formation (from early to mature state). The author's research, aims at understanding the phenomena of urbanization and deurbanization and related consequences as reflected in transformations in material culture and to critically examine literary data and corroborate this with available archaeological data; and finally to synthesize archaeo-historical evidence (Sawant 2006). The author has also dealt with various other facets of the Historical Archeology of Vidarbha (Sawant 2003, 2009, *in press* a, b, c).

Studies of Site Formation Processes in the Historical Context

V. Kathale (2009) at the Deccan College attempted to study site formation processes of historical sites (Bhon and Paturda in Buldhana district) in the Purna Basin by analyzing material remains with the help of chemical analysis (ph, organic carbon, phosphate, calcium carbonate etc.). She concludes, 'the chemical analysis of the samples taken from the different trenches on different mounds from Bhon show intense human activity on the Mound-I in the area of Trench B9 and D11 whereas Trench-D on Mound II shows less intense human activity. Similarly the areas of Stupa and Bandi (Brick manufacturing area) are the manufacturing areas where less human

activity is reflected in low phosphate content being religious and production centers respectively. This is a clear supportive evidence of the hypothesis that the different activities of human leave different signatures in term of phosphate content for longer period of time unless and until it is physically removed.' (Kathale 2009: 188).

Cultural Sequence of Vidarbha

Excavations in Vidarbha have established the cultural sequence, which is summarized here.

Chalcolithic

Very few sites have Chalcolithic deposits, e.g. Tuljapur Garhi (Bopardikar 1996), Adam (IAR 1990-91, 1991-92), Arambha (IAR 1991-92), and Shirikanda (IAR 1991-92). Of these, Tuljapur Garhi, is the only site in the Vidarbha which yielded Malwa and Jorwe phases similar to the Deccan Chalcolithic (Bopardikar 1996). Excavations at Adam brought to light, for the first time, a period called the 'Vidarbha Chalcolithic'. According to the excavator, Period II of Adam is ascribed to the Vidarbha Chalcolithic as the ceramic industry did not correspond either in form or in description with any contemporary Chalcolithic cultures of the region adjoining Vidarbha (for ceramic details see IAR 1988-89: 50-62).

Iron Age-Megalithic Period

Most excavations were conducted at Iron Age-Megalithic sites, and these highlighted their economy, technology, pottery, house types, etc (for details see Deo 1982, Joshi 1993, Mohanty and Joshi 1996). Problems regarding authorship, reasoning and theoretical approaches behind megalithic practices, differences (if any) between burial sites, burial-habitation sites, and habitation sites; and many more issues still remain to be addressed. Important features of the Iron Age-Megalithic period of Vidarbha include the extensive exploitation and multiple uses of iron. The presence of horses and horse-ornaments is an important characteristic of Vidarbha's Iron Age-Megalithic tradition and provides additional information on riding skills. Excellent craftsmanship is seen in the use of metals like gold, iron and copper. Important sites are Takalghat-Khapa, Mahurjhari, Arni, Khairwada, Naikund, Bhagimahari, Adam, Tharsa, Arambha, Shirikanda, Bhawar, Pachkheri, etc. (for details see Table 1).

Fig. 6: Megalithic burial from Mahurjhari reconstructed and preserved at IGRMS, Bhopal (courtesy R.K. Mohanty, Deccan College Annual Report 2004-05)

Mauryan Period

Few sites have yielded habitation deposits of the Mauryan period. These include Adam (IAR 1988-89: 50-62; 1990-91: 45-50; 1991-92: 63-68; Nath 1992a: 69-79), Arambha (IAR 1991-92: 73-74), Arni (IAR 1978-79: 71-72; 1984-85: 55-56), Bhawar (IAR 1992-93: 55-62), Bramhapuri (Sawant 2003, 2006), Kaundinyapur (Dikshit 1968), Mansar (Joshi and Sharma 2005: 1-16), Pachkheri (IAR 1991-92: 64-73), and Pauni (Deo and Joshi 1972, Nath 1998). Some coins which were assigned to rulers such as Chandragupta, Bindusara and Asoka of the Maurya dynasty are reported from Vidarbha (see Gupta 1963). Important punch-marked coin hoards are reported from Bhandara (1878), Malegaon (1921-22), Mangrul (1923), Umrer (see Gupta 1955) and Salebhatti (1933) (Jain 1957). Apart from these hoards, a few coin specimens, assigned to the Mauryan period, are also reported from Nevari (Dikshit 1964: 91-95), Kaundinyapur (Dikshit 1968: 136), Mana (Kothalakar 1992: 24-28), Hinganghat (Allan 1936: lii, 56; Durga Prasad 1934: Pl. 16 – Sr. no. 85, Pl. 21 – Sr. no. 142), and Pauni (Gupta 1971: 107- 108).

Apart from the Mauryan punch-marked coins, the Vidarbha region also yielded local varieties which are assigned to various *janapadas* such as Vidarbha, Andhra, Asmaka, Chedi (see for details - Rajgor 2001, type no. 494; Sawant 2003: 12; Kulkarni 2004a: 40, Kulkarni 2005: 19-36; Ramteke 2006: 68-87).

A very important epigraphic record of the Mauryan period was discovered at Deotek, a small village in Chandrapur district (discussed later in detail).

Pre-Satavahana Period

A shorter chronology (propounded by A.M. Shastri) is inclined to date the Satavahana rule to around the middle of the first century BCE, thus creating an interval of several centuries between the termination of the Mauryan power and the commencement of the Satavahana rule. A fairly large number of uninscribed cast and die-struck specie in cheap metals like copper, potin and lead were reported from Adam, Kaundinyapur, Pauni, Bhokardan, Nasik, Brahmpuri (Kolhapur), Kotalingala, amongst others. These are termed as Pre-Satavahana issues (Shastri 1982: 1-16; 2002: 64). Archaeological remains of the Pre-Satavahana period is well represented at two sites – Adam (IAR 1990-91: 45-50; 1991-92: 63-68) and Bhon (Deotare 2007; Deotare *et al.* 2007; Sawant 2006, Shete 2009). Both sites have unearthed large scale structural activities such as stupas, brick wells and ring wells and residential complexes along with other antiquities. As far as earlier excavations are concerned, the Pre-Satavahana period may have been confused with the Mauryan or Satavahan periods; as this phase was not clear. The coins of Pre-Satavahana rulers like Bhadra, Mitra (Nath 1990a: 48-57), Sebak (Mirashi 1945: 95; Thakur 2006: 2) and some unknown provincial ruler from Bhon (Sawant 2006) are reported from Vidarbha (see also Jha 2004a and 2004b). In addition, very recently, city issues of *Bhadravati* have been reported from Bhadravati, Chandrapur district (Kulkarni 2004b; Jha and Varma 2004; Gupta 2005).

Satavahana Period

The Satavahanas along with their contemporaries, namely, the Kshatrapas (Mirashi 1981; Shastri 2002) and Maharathis (Mangalam 1999, 2002a, 2002b) played an important role in the history of Vidarbha. Sites in Vidarbha which have yielded Satavahana deposits include Adam (IAR 1990-91: 45-50; 1991-92: 63-68) (Nath 1995: 149-171), Arambha (Nath 1992a: 69-74), Arni (IAR 1978-79: 71-72; 1984-85: 55-56), Bhawar (IAR 1992-93: 55-62), Bramhapuri (Walimbe 2003: 39-40; Sawant 2006), Kaundinyapur (Dikshit 1968: 29), Khairwada (IAR 1981-82: 51), Mandhal (Shastri 1978: 143), Mansar (Joshi and Sharma 2000: 127-131; 2005: 1-26), Pachkheri (IAR 1992-93: 64-73), Paunar (Deo and Dhavalikar 1967), Pauni (Deo and Joshi 1972; Nath 1998), and Ramtola (IAR 1969-70: 20).

As far as epigraphic records are concerned, two inscriptions are of importance, both from the site of Pauni. In 1935, a stone inscription was incised on a massive slab discovered at Pauni, (Mirashi 1942: 11-14; Deo and Joshi 1972: 9). The characters in inscriptions belong to the early Brahmi alphabets and a Prakrit language. V.V. Mirashi (1942: 11) assigned this inscription to the beginning of the Christian era. The inscription records the dedication of a slab with foot prints (*pajugapati*) by Bhagadatta (*Bhagadata*), the king of the Bhara clan. It is not known whether this clan was identical with the Bharasivas whose glorious achievements are recorded in the Vakataka inscriptions. In 1964 a pillar inscription of three lines in early Brahmi characters of the 2nd century CE and Prakrit language, was discovered during farming at Pauni. The object of the inscription was to record that the sculptured pillar (*chhaya-khambho*) was in the memory of Mahakshatrapa Kumara Rupiamma (Mirashi 1968c: 201-203).

The most common motif on Satavahana coins from Vidarbha is an elephant on the obverse and the Ujjain symbol on the reverse. These are noted on coins of Satavahana or Sadavahana (copper), Vasisthiputra Pulumavi (copper/lead), Vasisthiputra Satakarni (copper/lead), Siva Sri Pulumavi (lead), Siva Skanda Satakarni (lead), Gautamiputra Yajna Sri Satakarni (copper/potin/lead), Vijay Satakarni (elephant), Saka Satakarni (?), Karna Satakarni, Kumbha Satakarni (potin) (see Jha and Verma 2005; Mirashi 1961: 336-337; Sarma 1980). The Lakshmi type coin was reported from Kaundinyapur, attributed to Siri Satakarni (Dikshit 1968: 137). Some coins have a legend '*Satavahana*' or '*Sadavahana*'. Recent excavations at Bhon yielded a few inscribed coins, one of which lists the name of the issuer which reads as- '*Sadavahana*' (Sawant 2006: 132). Another type has a bold taurine, Ujjain symbol with a pellet inside and a legend '*no Siri Satavaha..*' (also of Siri Sati and Satakarni) on the obverse and a tree with leaves on the reverse (potin/bronze) (see Jha and Verma 2005). Two major hoards of Satavahana coins are recorded from Vidarbha, one from Chanda (Chandrapur district) (Rapson 1908: 21, 42, 48) and the other from Tarhala (Akola District) (Mirashi 1940: 83-94). Similarly, Kshatrapa coins were reported from various sites. Coins of Damajadasri III, Bhartadaman, Visvasena, Rudrasena III, Yasodaman, Rudrasimha II are reported from Akot, Karanja (Akola district), Washim, Bhatkuli (Amaravati district), Adam

(Nagpur district), and Paunar (Wardha district) (see Jha & Rajgor 1994; IAR 1962-63: 14; IAR 1987-88: 85; Mirashi 1960: 113-117, 1965: 94-96, 1968a: 92-95, 1971: 117-119, 1975: 152-153; Shastri 1974: 111-113, 1975: 154-157, 1979: 20-22). The most common type of coin displays the bust of a king on the obverse and on the reverse, the hill symbol in the centre with a wavy horizontal line signifying a river below, a crescent on the left and a star on the right near the top with legends on both sides (see Jha and Rajgor 1994).

Vakataka Period

The Vakatakas started ruling in Vidarbha and adjoining regions around the end of the third century CE and continued to rule upto the close of the 5th century CE (see Mirashi 1957, 1963; Shastri 1992, 1997). Sites such as Arambha (IAR 1991-92: 73-74; Nath 1992: 69-74), Arni (IAR 1984-85: 55-56), Hamalapuri (Sali 1998: 9), Kaundinyapur (Dikshit 1968), Mahurjhari (Hunter 1933: 30-35; Mohanty 2002: 45-47), Mandhal (Shastri 1978: 142-174), Mansar (IAR 1994-95: 55-57; Joshi and Sharma 2000: 127-131; Bakker 2002: 1-24), Mulchera (IAR 1988-89: 49), Nagara (IAR 1979-80: 50; Jamkhedkar 1983: 25-36), Paunar (Deo and Dhavalikar 1967), Pauni (Nath 1998: 9), Ramtek (Jamkhedkar 1983: 25-36), Shirkhanda (Sali 1998: 10), Tharsa (IAR 1989-90: 66-68), Vivekanandpur (Sali 1998: 9), Washim (Sali 1998:10-12) have yielded Vakataka deposits. Apart from this, the major source of information on the Vakataka period, comes from copper plates and stone inscriptions (Mirashi 1963; Shastri 1997). Though the Vakatakas were one of the important dynasties of the south, it is surprising that their coinage came to light very late as compared to their other accomplishments. It was assumed by some scholars that the Vakatakas did not issue any coins, but allowed coins of other rulers to circulate in their territory. This assumption was proved wrong in the light of new discoveries on Vakataka coinage (Shastri 1997: 136-146, Kulkarni 2003: 65-80, Meshram and Gajbhiye 2008: 65-67; for counter view see Goyal 2007: 1-15).

One of the important contributions of the Vakataka period is the development of Brahmanical iconography, which is reflected in beautiful sculptures (Fig. 7) and temple structures. Temple remains ascribed to the Vakatakas were unearthed at Paunar, Mandhal (3 brick shrines), and Ramtek (stone shrine) (district: Nagpur) and Nagra (one brick

shrine) (district: Bhandara). Mandhal shrines are the earliest examples of Vakataka architecture dated to c. 300-600 CE (Jamkhedkar 1988: 59-72; Bakker 1982, 2002). The history of the Vakatakas remains incomplete without a reference to Ajanta. The Ajanta caves have always been regarded as a synthesis of religion and art. According to Walter Spink (1992: 177- 202), the Vakataka king Harisena, who ruled from 460 CE to 477 CE, was fundamentally responsible for the development of Ajanta (Gupte and Mahajan 1962; Yazadani 1983; Spink 1972, 1981, 1992; Dhavalikar 1973). Most early historical sites in Vidarbha were deserted by the end of the Vakataka period, leaving a gap till the medieval period. Sites such as Adam, Arni, Bhon, Bhawar, Kaundinyapur, Khairwada, Mahurjhari, Mandhal, Pauni, Pachkheri, Shirkhanda, and Tharsa were occupied upto the Satavahana or the Vakataka periods but were deserted after that (see Sawant 2006).

Contribution to Buddhist History

On the basis of available archaeological evidence the spread of Buddhism in Vidarbha, can be dated to the Mauryan period, especially during Asoka's reign. Excavations at Pauni (Bhandara district) (Deo and Joshi 1972), Adam (Nagpur district) (Nath 1989: 97), and Bhon (Buldana district) (Deotare *et al.* 2007) (Fig. 8) unearthed evidence of *stupas*. New discoveries in the form of Buddhist sculptures or rock-cut caves are also reported (IAR 1994-95: 58; Meshram 1996). The role of Buddhism in Vidarbha was studied by S.B. Deo (1973b) and later more elaborately by P. Meshram of Nagpur University (Meshram 1993, 1994, 1996; Meshram *et al.* 2005).

Deotek, a village in Chandrapur district, about 50 miles southeast of Nagpur, yielded a large inscribed slab bearing two epigraphs, first published by J.D. Begler (1878a: 124-125). He noted: 'The first inscription consists of four lines, running longitudinally, [...] The characters are of the kind known as those of the Asoka edicts [...] The second inscription is in five lines running across the stone [...] this is in the early Gupta characters [...]' (Begler 1878: 124). Later, V.V. Mirashi published details of both inscriptions (Mirashi 1968b). One inscription dates to Asoka and the other to the Vakatakas. The inscription of the Asokan period records the command of some lord (*Sami*) who prohibits the capture and slaughter (evidently of some animals in certain seasons as in Asoka's 5th pillar edict, or

throughout the year) and declares a punishment for those who dared disobey. The third line mentions executive officers (*amacha = amatyah*) whose duty may have been to enforce these orders. The last line contains the date 14, denoting probably the regnal year in which the record was incised. In some of his inscriptions (e.g. Rupnath Rock Inscription), Asoka orders his officers to get his edicts engraved on stone pillars, rocks and stone slabs throughout districts in their charge. The Deotek inscription probably is the only instance of its kind (Mirashi 1968b: 125-134). With the exception of the Sopara inscription, this is the only inscription of the Asokan period from Maharashtra. What is important in this inscription is the order of prohibition of capture and slaughter of animals which was the theme of Asokan edicts.

The site of Mansar, Nagpur was excavated by A.K. Sharma (former Superintending Archaeologist, ASI) and J.P. Joshi (former DG, ASI) since 1997-98 (IAR 1997-98). Initially the excavators declared that the site was of Buddhist importance with Stupa and viharas. The on-site museum and research centre was entitled, 'The Bodhisattva Nagarjuna Memorial Research Centre and Museum'. It is now clear that it is an important site of the Vakataka period and the excavator has identified it with ancient 'Pravarapura' (capital of Vakatakas) (Joshi and Sharma 2005: 1-26).

Conclusion

From the very beginning of archaeological research in Vidarbha, great emphasis was given to Megalithic sites. Archaeologists attempted to stress the unique nature of individual megalithic sites. However, no one attempted to examine their importance in a regional perspective and to study the Iron Age to Early Historic transition. What is important to note, is that most excavated sites in Vidarbha belong to the Iron Age-Megalithic period, although very few attempts were made to explain the phenomena of megaliths with a problem-oriented approach.

Few attempts were made to reconstruct the history of Vidarbha combining archaeology, historical information and literature. Such a holistic approach is necessary to understand cultural transformation processes, namely, the Early Iron Age and Early Historic transformations and subsequent stages in the political, social, religious and economical development in Vidarbha.

Fig. 7: Varah from Ramtek, Nagpur

Historical sites were often neglected at the cost of studying Iron Age sites. As a result, very few historical sites were excavated as compared with Megalithic sites. This is probably the reason why the Early Historic period of Vidarbha remained ignored. Today favorable changes are taking place, as various organizations such as the Deccan College, Nagpur University, the ASI, and the MSDAM, are excavating historical sites which will prove information in developing rational and logical explanations on cultural processes in Vidarbha.

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Fig. 8: Stupa structure at Bhon (Courtesy B.C. Deotare)

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